

RESPONSE PAPER

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

HOW TO WRITE ACADEMIC PAPERS

1) **INTRODUCTION**

Writing essays and academic papers are a requirement for students continuing their undergraduate, graduate and postgraduate degrees. Writing can be a challenging process especially when students come from international contexts where English is not their native language. There are several suggestions, however, that can make writing clear and concise papers easier for students. This paper aims to go through some of those suggestions based on the EUCLID ACA-401D coursepack for period one (1).

2) **WHAT IS AN ACADEMIC PAPER?**

Academic papers are papers that students continuing their education are required to write as part of their course requirements for graduation. One important feature of these papers is that they need to be based on evidence to persuade readers on the argument or question on hand (EUCLID 2019, 1).

3) **WHAT ARE SOME OF THE SUGGESTIONS TO WRITE A GOOD ACADEMIC PAPER?**

When I often write papers, I find the early start of writing very difficult as I try to decide on the question I want to handle and to make this question as specific as possible. I often find it much less stressful to start working on papers a minimum of one week ahead of the deadline. This will allow me to take my time in identifying my argument, discussing

it with colleagues, researching my topic and most importantly have some time to revise my drafts. While this is true for me, other writers might have a different approach to writing. Although the suggestions below are based on the EUCLID ACA-401D coursepack for period 1, it is important to note these suggestions are not set in stone. Different writers may follow different suggestions, however, what remains important is that regardless of the suggestions followed, all writers need to produce a final paper built on a clear and concise evidence-based thesis. Below are some suggestions to write academic papers:

a) Identify your thesis

The first step in writing an essay or academic paper is to define the thesis or argument under question. Defining the thesis means the writer is clear on what she or he is going to argue in the paper. This requires analysis of the research question. The thesis should preferably be mentioned in the introductory paragraph and the writer must choose the right wording when phrasing the thesis (EUCLID 2019, 14). For example, when the writer says “I will analyze the various health insurance schemes ...” it is different than saying “I will argue that social health insurance is the preferable option to...” While the first thesis statement needs to look at different insurance schemes, the second will focus mostly on the social health insurance scheme and needs to provide evidence on why it is the preferable option.

b) Be structured and remain focused

After identifying the thesis and conducting some research about it, the writer will prepare an outline of the paper. Based on this outline, the writer will begin discussing the relevant aspects of the thesis in a focused and structured manner. This means the focus of the discussion will be on relevant aspects of the thesis rather than on all issues around the thesis topic regardless of their importance or relevancy (EUCLID 2019, 14). Losing focus would mean the reader will get confused and accordingly consider the paper of poor quality.

c) Write in a clear way

Writing clearly can be a challenging process, but if writing is not clear then the reader will miss your point. Some tips to write clearly would be to make writing as simple as possible. For example, writing a scientific paper might mean you will be using scientific terms provided your target audience is familiar with those terms. However, if for example, you are writing a paper on management for the general public, you can make it simple by using words any reader can understand. Another way to write clearly is by using short sentences and by dividing long paragraphs into two (EUCLID 2019, 14-15).

d) Support your arguments with evidence

When you write papers you will need to support your arguments with evidence from credible sources (EUCLID 2019, 1). Evidence might be in the form of statistics and figures, theories already proven by other writers or in other forms. You will need to reference your evidence in the paper. This does not necessarily mean that you will need to quote another writer you are referring to. Quotations should be used only as they bring significance to your paper (EUCLID 2019, 15).

e) Avoid plagiarism

Plagiarism happens when a writer uses the same words as another writer without quoting the passage or sentence. Adding a footnote is not considered enough and the writer must use quotations if the same wording of the passage is used. Additionally, one needs to note that avoiding plagiarism while paraphrasing paragraphs means writers need to re-write the passage in their way. Simply changing a word or two is not considered paraphrasing and would mean that the passage needs to be referenced. Plagiarism will result in punitive actions (EUCLID 2019, 16).

f) Review your drafts

After you finish your first draft, put it on the side for some time and then review it. It is also a good idea to have a colleague review your document. This will help you to understand if your writing is clear and if other readers can understand your point. Once sure you have done all your edits, submit your final product.

4) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, writing can be a challenging process but there are several tips a writer can follow to make writing easier and more informative. This paper presented some key suggestions based on the EUCLID ACA-401D coursepack for period one (1). Other sources may include other suggestions. The key message here is that regardless of the writing tips followed, the final paper a writer produces needs to be based on an evidence-based thesis and should persuade the reader of the main argument. Another main message is that writers need to avoid plagiarism while writing papers or otherwise will become subject to sanctions. Tips addressed in this paper will help in formulating structured papers that are easy to comprehend and follow.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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